

Swarms projects workshop

Strategic vision report

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Introduction

Members of the EUCloudEdgeIoT community met on 5th September 2024 in Brussels for a workshop¹ organised by the European Commission. It was to discuss intermediate results of the projects of the Swarm Intelligence cluster and beyond.

The workshop took stock of the progress of the swarms technologies and discussed the horizontal aspects of the cluster such as architectures, standardization and interoperability, platform building, open source, market insights, communications and dissemination. In the same time, it focused on the priority sectors such as energy, mobility/transport logistics and industrial/manufacturing.

The workshop brought together research project representatives, experts and stakeholders to discuss the results of the ongoing synergistic efforts in the EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative (EUCEI) and delineate future directions of the computing continuum as well as priority actions for the actors involved. Participants of the workshop included the Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) UNLOCK-CEI, Nexusforum, HiPEAC and Discover US, European Commission representatives, coordinators all five swarms projects, representatives of the MetaOS and other related projects and project review experts.

The swarm technologies and technical challenges

The swarms projects (Topic HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-03: Programming tools for decentralised intelligence and swarms - RIA) tackle future challenges to emerging, distributed edge nodes with decentralised intelligence and/or swarm behaviour. They address the ever-increasing needs of future, dynamic IoT systems with a higher computing capacity at the edge. The focus of the projects is on new abstraction models and CPS, next generation IoT based on new communication paradigms and/or embedding lightweight AI/ML technologies and concepts based on new computing paradigms like neuromorphic computing.

Decentralised intelligence and a self-organization ability in this cluster are needed to adapt IoT and edge systems to varying environmental conditions, to scale efficiently, and to provide resilient operation for the sustainability of the system. The next generation system design of components, devices / sensor networks, architectures and technologies of these projects support edge computing applications. They embed AI/ML processing capacity, and enable collaboration among IoT nodes. Such solutions drive the digital transformation of key societal and industrial sectors such as smart energy, mobility, smart farming, healthy living, automotive, smart city and the overall spectrum of Industrial IoT.

The focus of the projects can be presented by the following 4 categories:

¹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/swarms-workshops-in-bruxelles>

CPS and IoT

These projects implement emerging methods for node and system abstraction, in order to cope with the complexity of programming distributed systems, AI-driven systems, or systems with swarm behaviour. New software tools like aggregate programmed, behaviour- or rule-driven programming environments and languages are included. The key idea is to simplify the software development by programming a large and distributed system in a safe, secure, and dynamic way, predicting quality of services and distributed decision making. Tools and languages are to abstract from the dynamic interaction of underlying IoT nodes. Applying new methods for these nodes that can be modelled as a swarm of simpler devices or can integrate swarm-based algorithms to achieve some global goals. In this way, starting from simple rules for individual behaviours and interactions among individuals, a global optimum is achieved at system-level. Many of the methods applied, deal with adapters to the underlying devices or virtual abstractions that are tightly coupled with the behaviour of smart IoT nodes, while others are concerned with the design of intelligent Multi-Agent Systems that take inspiration from the collective behaviour of a group of nodes.

Convincing contributions were made in terms of new Programming environments for smart edge-connected nodes and dynamic groups of nodes across the device-edge-cloud continuum, which apply abstraction models and novel software technologies.

AI-IoT

These projects are based on new IoT nodes and edge computing. The projects bring computational resources and services to the network edge close to the user devices, lowering latency and connecting with cloud computing resources. Unlike the previous category, AI-IoT resources in the projects are based on constrained and heterogeneous nodes with new mesh communication techniques to deal with unstable connectivity. Projects of this category feature synergies of the integration of IoT, AI and edge computing, paving the way for new types of (tensor) processing units becoming pervasive.

Use cases of these areas dealt with IoT devices that measure health-related parameters, such as smart activity trackers, smart watches, smart building devices, power grids, and traffic lights, environmental sensors for condition-monitoring for farms and other industrial applications.

5G

Some projects explore new network functionality and in-network computing, in most cases on emerging 5G networks. Edge computing environments base their communication infrastructure on Software-Defined Network (SDN), on Radio Access Network (RAN), or on a composition of these technologies like Open RAN, exploiting network functions such as ad-hoc cloud/fog communication not limited to 5G as their objective. Although the edge layer supports all layers from cloud to edge to IoT, the architectures largely support networking of edge and near cloud computing devices.

Computing Paradigms

These projects are targeting radical new computing paradigms like quantum computing, osmotic computing, or neuromorphic computing of which lightweight versions should be developed and integrated into a wider IoT or CPS ecosystem.

The swarms cluster

The swarms cluster comprises of 5 projects INCODE², TaRDIS, OASEES, OpenSwarm and SMARTEDGE. They have been awarded EU financing of 37 mil EUR. in the framework of the evaluation of the topic HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-03: Programming tools for decentralised intelligence and swarms (RIA), which took place in 2022.

Allocation of the EC contributions to the swarms cluster project in EUR.

OpenSwarm	5,860,171
INCODE	7,999,485
SMARTEDGE	7,912,285
TaRDIS	7,259,663
OASEES	7,987,425
TOTAL	37,019,030

The call³ topic asked for agile and secure architectures for collaborative smart nodes with decentralised or swarm intelligence, which build on European strengths in embedded sensors and devices and wireless communication, both non-cellular and mobile 5G networks. Further outcomes are to be programming environments for smart edge-connected nodes and dynamic groups of nodes across the device-edge-cloud continuum as well as dynamic open environments and tools, which stimulate open architectures and interfaces, interoperability and avoiding vendor lock-in, open source.

The selected projects of the swarms cluster cover well these technology requirements. They involve networks with minimum hierarchy, but also with high diversity and heterogeneity in scope, type, connectivity, capabilities (compute, storage, power); cloud at the top hierarchy level. The networks with geographic distribution of sensing IoT devices in settings such as a city, farm or factory, increasingly include moving end nodes – e.g. drones, trucks. Nodes are connected to edge devices, which in turn communicate with cloud. Swarm networks display distribution of processing towards the edge and connected devices, sharing a command structure between components and increasingly independent from a management

² It is to be noted that the INCODE project changed name in September 2024 to P2CODE.

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl4-2022-data-01-03>

layer (autonomous or automated). The projects give also insight into some comparisons between the energy consumed on processing and the energy consumed on transmission. Reduction of the energy consumed on transmission is provided for by dynamic task offloading scenarios in the pilots. The task offloading decision algorithm determines whether to offload tasks to edge servers rather than cloud servers, potentially leading to energy savings by optimizing resource utilization and minimizing transmission of data.

The swarms projects have then been launched in January 2023 and will be implemented in the period until the end of 2025. Exception is Openswarm project which will end in April 2026. The swarms projects are building onto the results of projects of two previous calls. Namely, the European Commission financed previously financed calls H2020-ICT-56-2020 Next Generation Internet of Things (RIA)⁴ and HORIZON-CL4-2021-DATA-01-05: Future European platforms for the Edge: Meta Operating Systems (RIA)⁵, which can be considered as the predecessors of the swarms projects. A MetaOS projects are focused on sharing resources in the continuum, supporting a swarm to share application commands autonomously on top of the managed infrastructure. Prior to these two calls, more deployment projects were financed in the areas of health, energy and agriculture (see figure below).

Timeline of the implementation of the HE edge computing projects and IoT pilots by cluster

The edge computing applications are capable of managing the heterogeneity and of application of novel methodologies that can cope with the complexity and uncertainty of these new systems. Despite distributed network model of swarms, a centralized authority is needed to handle security and privacy,

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/ict-56-2020>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl4-2021-data-01-05>

coordinating authorization, access control, and data sharing across different edges. Decisions on where to place security controls—locally on devices or centralized in the cloud—can significantly impact the system's ability to respond to and recover from attacks.

There are altogether 28 use cases in the swarms projects. They cover the sectors of energy, climate, mobility, transport and logistics, agriculture, crisis disaster management, smart homes, healthcare however the highest number of the use cases involve industrial applications. (see figure below)

Sector coverage of the use cases of the swarms cluster

Project acronym	Energy	Climate / Buildings	Mobility	Transport / Logistics	Industrial	Agriculture	Food supply	Crisis Disaster Man.	Smart homes/city	Healthcare
OpenSwarm	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	
INCODE	X			X	X					
SMARTEDGE			X		X					X
TaRDIS	X			X	X				X	
OASEES	X	X			X					X
	X				X					

Swarm effects and industrial up-take in energy

The workshop examined the European energy sector which is undergoing significant transformation, diversification and digitalisation. The industry is ambitiously adopting automation and remote management using IoT. Its strategic nature, rapid transformation, and distributed assets make it a suitable application area for use cases in the context of CEI. A recent survey conducted by UNLOCK-CEI showed that we can expect rapid adoption of edge computing over the next few years in many sectors, including energy.

From the energy domain perspective, swarm behaviours mainly emerge in the context of renewable energy resources, such as wind turbines and solar home systems. For example, a swarming effect in wind turbines consists of turbines communicating with and learning from each other towards the entire wind-farm optimization, e.g., in terms of turbine load, maintenance, and reaction to meteorology changes.

The example of the OASEES use case in the figure below aims to extend the capabilities of wind turbines, to be able to function as an IoT device in swarm mode in order to reduce the costs of maintenance. Simultaneous capture and data processing from several smart edge nodes at the wind turbines' location, reducing processing time. The acquired data will be processed at the edge, and analysed using machine learning algorithms so that the sensors are able to learn from each other (improved calibration, noise suppression, etc.) using federated learning based on cloud and edge nodes, to improve and obtain better metrics while optimizing the failure prediction on the blades of the wind turbine. The pilot will also address the aspect of Object IDs, via the assignment of Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) for each wind turbine, and the relevant privacy and trust among different edge devices. As devices will only share the absolute required data and not their entire identity. Maintenance of wind farms represents a reduction cost of 20% for 15-20 years of maintenance. OASEES swarm network devices are able to analyse and predict blade failures, therefore extend their lifetime. Hence, the swarm network improves sustainability by avoiding a complex recyclability process and reducing environmental waste from the process.

Use case of Smart Energy harvesting and Predictive Maintenance Wind turbines using Disease Edge/Swarm Intelligence of the OASEES project

A recent promising concept is swarm electrification. Its central idea is the peer-to-peer energy sharing of surplus energy in solar home systems to connect additional neighbors and grow a bottom-up grid. It builds a micro-grid, but rather than a planned network, it is assembled in an ad-hoc manner, connecting available equipment and growing organically as more resources become available, thus lowering the investments needed for a traditional community grid. The aim would be to maximise the benefits of this solar revolution by utilizing existing equipment and providing the most cost-effective energy connections. Key challenges include improved modelling to better examine the swarm behaviour, scalability, and stability of swarm grids, along with improved battery maintenance strategies and new business models to encourage investment.

From the computational swarm intelligence perspective, popular algorithmic models present in the literature (that imitate the principles of large groups of simple swarm individuals working together to achieve a goal through self-learning, self-adjusting, and mutual cooperation manners) are ant colony optimization (ACO) and particle swarm optimization (PSO). With the increasing deployment of AI-based techniques, federated learning (or collaborative learning) solutions are nowadays very popular in managing computational intelligence in distributed contexts. In the energy sector, computational swarm intelligence is typically used for optimization purposes, e.g., optimizing EV's recharging schedule, reducing the cost of maintenance, estimating electricity energy demand, defining optimal grid configurations and expansion planning.

Popular use cases in the energy sector mainly focus on: i) Smart grid, where swarm intelligence is finalized to improve grid efficiency and support, integration of renewable energy sources and smart energy harvesting, reduction in energy costs, reduction of cost for maintenance; ii) EV chargers, where swarm intelligence is finalized to optimization of EV charging schedules, reduction in energy costs; iii) drone-based observation/inspection, where swarm intelligence is finalized to reduction of cost for maintenance.

Furthermore, the use cases presented at the workshop in the energy sector addressed by four of the five projects in the Swarms Cluster to demonstrate the benefits of the developed programming platform and tools belong to the above listed categories.

Swarm use cases in the energy sector

OpenSwarm - Renewable Energy Community

Renewable Energy Community: the focus is on adaptable interaction of energy consumers and producers for new business opportunities and contribution to decarbonisation. Distributed swarm intelligence is adopted in the orchestration between the smart sensors (the devices) and the customer gateway (the edge).

INCODE - Utilities inspection

Utilities inspection: the focus is on two functionalities, namely predictive maintenance and intruder/equipment failure, applied to the HV substation. While the aim is to bring intelligence at the edge (e.g., for smart data analytics and AI/ML algorithms to identify power event), the swarm effect is not explicitly identified.

OASEES - Smart energy harvesting and EV fleet and grid optimization

Smart energy harvesting and predictive maintenance wind turbines using edge/swarm intelligence: the goal is to optimize the energy production of wind turbines and to extend their useful life through the prediction and detection of failures in the blades. The approach is

based on extending the capabilities of the Blade Acoustic Monitoring System (BAMS), so to be able to function as an IoT device in swarm mode that allows the simultaneous capture and processing of data from a considerable number of wind turbines, leading to the creation of a BAMS network.

TaRDIS - Multi-level smart charging

Multi-level smart charging: the goal is to overcome the grid imbalance arising from EV charging. TaRDIS proposes a multi-level smart charging, divided into three core layers: the Edge (HEMS, EV chargers); the Fog (end-users community or building level aggregator); and the Cloud (centralised controlling systems, SCADA). The energy community orchestrator manages requests from different consumers and prosumers, seen as a heterogeneous swarm in the Energy Community.

Although most of the defined use cases presented at the workshop show a degree of swarm effect, at this stage of development the solutions the projects offer to manage it do not appear to exploit fully computational decentralized intelligence at the edge. For example, the current network organization adopted by the OpenSwarm project seems still hierarchical with potentially sharing the energy between neighbours in a collaborative manner, so the swarm effect appears limited.

Although there are use cases that employ similar approaches towards the swarm effect (e.g., orchestrators based on federated learning), the specific aspects addressed in the energy sector do not allow to assess at this development stage whether there are components of a project's framework that can be immediately reused in the energy use case of another project.

Swarm effects and industrial up-take in mobility

Swarms can be defined as any set (not necessarily homogeneous) of assets operating in the field which can benefit from being considered as a cluster of communicating instances in a way that the behaviour and the performance of each asset, but also of the whole cluster, can be dynamically optimised towards the execution and achievement of a common goal, can be seen as having a swarm effect.

Thus fleet of cars, park of wind turbines, PV installations, etc. can have a swarm effect if managed as such. Mobility is understood very broad by the project use cases presented at the workshop, but without clearly categorising and characterising their common and specific features, requirements and challenges. There are many different forms of swarm effect in the context of mobility i.e., homogeneous highly dynamic swarms of interacting vehicles or highly-heterogeneous (vertical) swarms along the whole value chain of logistics applications.

Swarm use cases in the mobility sector

OpenSwarm - Moving Network in Trains Shifting freight traffic of goods from road to rail ; Shifting passenger traffic from air to rail ; Develop a reconfigurable network of sensor nodes, distributed across the entire train, which interacts with stationary rail infrastructure. must be easy to install, require little and predictable maintenance, and be able to perceive the condition of the train as a whole.

INCODE - smart logistics at terminal stations through application-level programmability
Logistics and transport quality value chain The goal is to evaluate scenarios for smart logistics at terminal stations (hubs) with transported product quality assurance guaranties, optimal loading/unloading scheduling, safe working environment, end-user intervention through application-level programmability.

SmartEdge - driving assist cooperative perception. This demo will showcase the SMARTEDGE solution in the area of automotive, focusing on cooperative perception in building Advanced Driving Assistance System (ADAS) in terms of explaining road-user movements and real-time test cases generation at high-level abstractions.

SmartEdge - connected vehicles I2V intelligence swarm We will demonstrate the I2V operations by implementing two-way communication (via WP4) between road infrastructure (signal controllers) and connected vehicles. In particular, the expected time of change in traffic signals state is sent in advance to the connected vehicles (I2V). In addition, a vehicle may send its own speed, position and sensor information to the traffic control system (V2I).

TARDIS - Distributed navigation concepts for LEO satellite constellations This use-case consists in proposing on-board orbit determination and time synchronisation (ODTS) distributed navigation concept for LEO satellite constellations, based on ISL technologies, to demonstrate an autonomous TaRDIS navigation method leveraging the distribution and potential connectivity of satellites in a constellation architecture to provide an alternative and enhanced navigation solution to classical GNSS systems. Such solutions have high requirements on correctness, and their development is non-trivial and time consuming, being made even more complex by the nature of satellite hardware and communication mechanisms available to them.

Use case of smart logistics at terminal stations of the INCODE project

In the INCODE project, Load information including transport conditions data (perishables like food) flow from mobile IoT sensors of the truck fleet in real time or also periodically (e.g. daily) to register and authenticate with the local data centre at the warehouse. Static IoT sensors in the warehouse provide inventory status info. Some of the local data is combined with the cloud intelligence (logistics app). Then the local data centre receives commands to manage a swarm of end-devices / vehicles for (un)loading of the trucks according to a schedule or in real time.

Optimised (un)loading scheduling and allocation of respective resources in the INCODE project lead to prevention of damage to perishables and to reduced units costs of using trucks and loading vehicles. In turn, this leads to increased profits of the logistics actors. Logistics app is a trusted framework for all the logistics actors: road carriers, customs, warehouses, distributors or retailers. Coordinated (un)loading provides for work safety and prevents product mishandling.

Many of the use cases are not reflecting the complexity of real-world application contexts and appear very much as toy examples. There is so much research in the domain of distributed intelligence, as an overarching topic, with enormous progress in the different years. The cluster of projects presented during the workshop are mostly focusing on sensorisation and realisation of software platforms, while much more innovation could be generated with data-driven reasoning and AI. There are certainly many more advanced data-driven and machine learning approaches tackling similar application areas.

For sure, the projects should have expertise and proven track record in complex even processing, data and AI in their consortium or seek more synergies with external partners.

It is necessary to consider stronger engagement with end users and problem owners, i.e., partners benefiting from the development of realistic use cases and feeding the research with domain knowledge and feedback.

The projects should aim at researching at conceptual level the problem at hand, which involves mapping the applied problem to a higher level conceptual environment, composed of well scoped building blocks, specifying their functionality and interactions and thus arriving at the development of reference methodology with a broader application perspective. From what was presented during the workshop it does not seem that many common building blocks will be produced for the mobility sector.

The Swarms projects approach stems the development of a common software platform, while the MetaOS cluster seems to focus more on some sort of “virtual” ad-hoc swarm. A metaOS projects are focused on sharing resources in the continuum, supporting a swarm to share application commands autonomously on top of this managed infrastructure. This complementarity can be exploited further for widening the scope of what is understood by swarm effect.

Swarm effects and industrial up-take in manufacturing

Swarm Intelligence in manufacturing realizes the collective behaviour of intelligent decentralized self-organized components, such as stationary machining, fixed and mobile robots, ground vehicles, and humans that collaborate autonomously to perform mission-critical tasks without a central infrastructure. The dynamic machine-to-machine cooperation can help to improve several aspects in manufacturing plants. For example, mobile robots will understand their environment at a semantic level and share that knowledge with other robots in the swarm, allowing them to collectively solve problems. Moreover, swarm intelligence in smart factories can be used to implement a safer working environment taking measures to prevent accidents by detecting fatigue and stress of the workers and reducing the machine task-scheduling and factory pace in accordance. Another safety measure that can be implemented through swarm intelligence in smart factories is closely monitoring the distance between workers and machines/robots and stopping robots to avoid injuries. In addition, swarm intelligence can relieve human operators from burdensome tasks relevant to line supervision, configuration and reconfiguration, and quality control.

Another improvement refers to production agility, as the swarm behaviour of production machinery can allow for a quick reaction to changing market demands (agility). Also flexibility can benefit, allowing production rates scaling according to the varying production orders within short time at low costs. Moreover, collective behaviour of swarms may allow real-time optimization of resource usage, modular production with reduced CO₂, and waste reduction.

Swarm use cases in the industrial/manufacturing sector

OpenSwarm - Environment, Health, and Safety in industrial production sites Establish a self-contained, self-organizing swarm sensor network based on the OpenSwarm technology stack

for representative industrial manufacturing site. A heterogeneous group of entities (e.g., moving equipment like transport robots and workpiece carries, humans, static locations of interest) will be equipped with OpenSwarm-enabled devices that gather environmental data (incl. sound level, vibrations, CO2 level). The gathered data will be used to deliver live monitoring of the overall state by the established collaborative EHS network. SIG

INCODE - Smart factories – worker intelligent assistance An “Operator 4.0” prototype is deployed including smart wearable devices and services to manage and improve adaptive human-machine interaction. The deployment is performed at MADE industrial testing facilities, “Human machine interaction – Operator 4.0” area, and allows monitoring of operator/worker behaviour including (and not limited to) positioning, vital signs, status and workload. MADE

INCODE - Communities and PPDR Two edge nodes participate in this use case, located at a distance but within a targeted demonstration area with each one connected with different UAV/UGVs that need to cooperate. The INCODE Edge platform is ad-hoc deployed in the 5G O-RAN-IoT edges enabling the cooperation of the robotic platforms and drones. O-RAN technology will be used for hosting xApps and parts of distributed intelligence while depending on backhaul connectivity, core clouds also offer resources for decision support. UWS

SMARTEDGE - Smart Factories with Intelligent Mobile Robots This use case aims to demonstrate how heterogenous devices on the factory floor can work together in a peer-to-peer fashion to autonomously solve problems, without the intervention of humans, operators, or central control systems, by having a common high-level semantic understanding of their environment and the ability to take pre-emptive action based on semantic rules. TUB

SMARTEDGE - The low-code edge intelligence use case aims to demonstrate a low-code approach for realizing intelligent apps at the Edge. The approach is based on standardized semantic interfaces for IoT devices, continuous semantic integration of heterogenous devices on the factory floor, AI for constrained devices, and a low-code creation and orchestration of swarm intelligent apps. With this approach the Edge becomes not only intelligent, but also flexible. SAG

OASEES - Drone swarm over 5G for high mast inspection OASEES will integrate the DAO paradigm for the self-organised operation of a drone swarm, which will rely on the tight consolidation of the networking (5G-RedCap, 6LoWPAN) and edge acceleration technologies (SNN). Each of these two systems shall benefit from the presence of the other: for instance, the networking system should be able to find better transmission channels towards neighbours and/or better end-to-end paths towards faraway drones. The SNNs in this case will serve as a

power efficient accelerator technology mounted in the drone, to provide fast and accurate detection of most defects and communicate them back to the OASEES monitoring backend.

OASEES - Robotic swarm powered smart factory for I4.0 Implement an automated manufacturing process for semi-finished wood panels to be transferred from one station to the sanding machine and from the sanding machine to the other station via AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicles), coordinated and programmed by the OASEES orchestrator and SDK for line supervision, thus quickly implementing line configuration and reconfiguration inputs and relieving human operators from burdensome tasks. SCM

The example of the use case in the figure of the INCODE project below presents smart worker assistant in factories of the INCODE project.

Use case of smart worker assistant of the INCODE project

This use case includes the demonstration of novel technology use (IoT sensors, collaborative robots, wearables, exoskeletons), capable of detecting variables that indicate a danger / risk situation for the operator and reacting by modifying the work environment. In the smart worker in the loop action

sequence, high-resolution data is collected by IoT sensors/sensors applied to operators working in a smart factory and then pre-processed and recorded. Data is sent to edge node for advanced processing (e.g., enhanced workforce scheduling analytics). Appropriate indications for fatigue related indicators are generated and visualized. The production system is reinstructed to handle a change by slowing down the production speed of the line until the operator's parameters return to their usual set.

The gains of such an approach will include the introduction of actions triggered by vital signs that can detect and optimize workers' position based on production floor operational needs, safer working environment due to prevented accidents, improved labour efficiency due to better informed & directed workers and improved maintenance and fault detection times.

All the Swarm cluster projects engaged with the European Cloud-Edge-IoT (EuCEI). Therefore, there is a strong potential for designing common building blocks and reusing software and tools, but so far each project has been building its own platform. Recently, some consortia have been exploring synergies between their projects. About common building blocks, the Swarm projects results that would be needed include a layer for decentralized intelligence and coordination at the edge devices level, open APIs, and orchestrators.

Relying on open source components is the key for enabling customized developments and integrations, paving also the way to common standards. In this context, the TARDIS toolbox could provide some common building blocks, E.G., the programming model for developing decentralised and heterogeneous swarm systems.

Synergies are also expected between the Swarm intelligence cluster and the MetaOS one, to manage large-scale, distributed environments more effectively and flexibly. Swarm principles can drive resource discovery to execute applications or commands, across a continuum under a MetaOS, that supports enabling of load balancing and energy efficiency. Swarm collective behaviour can be also leveraged to improve operational flexibility and fault-tolerance.

Swarm approach for fleet coordination in the cluster

During the workshop, there were several projects with fleet coordination involved. In Wind turbines field, the swarms effect is materialized by detecting climate/wind changes early by the turbine at the edge of the field. The information is spread along the field to other turbines to anticipate orientation and operating mode of the rest of the field. That could be considered as a specific target objective of TARDIS project.

In industrial logistic: internal movements of industrial assets (IoT devices) could be managed avoiding collision and accident by swarm effect communication between device . That is /could be a specific target objective of INCODE project.

Safety and collision avoidance in road traffic light, horizontal and direct communication between traffic light and vehicle is alerting of the relevance of change to RED light to prepare the stop of the car. This

implies a real horizontal communication spontaneously between field devices (traffic lights, cars, other asset to define). Such emergency communication leads to a swarm based self-adaptative car traffic safety control.

Swarm use cases in the fleet coordination

OASEES - Swarm behavior is not detected as there is a centralized control. EVs fleet coordinated recharging to support optimal operation of electricity grid. The pilot will demonstrate the capability of deploying and coordinating in a scalable yet near real time way the operation and management of swarms of IoT-based devices, which will be coordinated and programmed through the OASEES SDK and orchestration platform. The EMOT EV fleet operator and respective EV drivers' community manager, will optimize EVs' recharging schedule to address local technical requirements from the electricity grid operator (ASM), in presence of local congestion, or local planned or unplanned maintenance of electricity grid branches.

TARDIS - Swarm behavior is managed by Community Orchestrator. Highly resilient factory shop floor digitalisation. This use case will be implemented in a real factory (an ACT customer) and comprises several production lines, a warehouse, an intralogistics fleet, an order management system, a setup and repair management system, and a business intelligence (BI) system.

TaRDIS - Highly resilient factory shop floor digitalisation. This use case will be implemented in a real factory (an ACT customer) and comprises several production lines, a warehouse, an intralogistics fleet, an order management system, a setup and repair management system, and a business intelligence (BI) system.

Swarm behavior managed by Community Orchestrator and Dynamic swarm constitution can be identified in the autonomous mobile robots fleet management where swarm nodes can borrow sensor streams from other nodes and share data processing tasks between swarm nodes. Swarm intelligence takes the full advantage of the swarm without the need of centralized control and global model. It provides a great solution for large scale application.

Swarm orchestrator concept and component from TARDIS project could be inspiring for and reused in other projects. Traffic management and V2X is a highly relevant field of experimentation and requirements for Swarm manifestation: So it seems necessary to Investigate the V2X standardization and current projects to build on / to orient toward Swarm data and communication model specification. The concept of Things Description database (TDD) of SmartEdge project is relevant for usage in other swarm oriented project.

Swarm inspired applications presented at the work shop are most of all based on Data Driven communication basis using MQTT broker, standard for IoT Messaging. Many IoT / Edge project use MQTT

broker data bus, so it could be interesting and helping to work on an enhanced and standardized MQTT based Control/command model that could validate/promote a swarm concept. MQTT with sparkplug specification for the payload formatting and semantic application domain is also relevant. Open Source COATY, a framework for collaborative IoT presented at the workshop by OpenSwarm could maybe be an entry point to this approach.

All swarms projects employ either Kubernetes or docker based deployment solution at the edge. However, a kind of Kubernetes for Device-level OS software deployment is missing with specific features like device-to-device enabled communication.

Role of Open Source in the cluster

Open Source is central to a buildup of autonomous swarm systems. Therefore, numerous Open-Source initiatives are members of EU-CEI ecosystem.

All projects seem to follow an open-source strategy. The issue is that some industries, especially security relevant, are reluctant in adopting open-source code running in their products for several reasons (licensing, viability, certification etc.). If there are frontrunners from big industry in critical infrastructure e.g., it would be good to promote them (e.g. the ECLIPSE presentation). This problem does not account for the tool development and SDKs, as open-source solutions are highly accepted by the industry (e.g. ECLIPSE SDK). In terms of security open source is a risk in presence of supply chain infiltration attacks (see "XZ-Uutils backdoor" discovered in 2023). It seems that the swarm projects either ignore or are not aware of this critical issue. Industry players are aware of this risk and they may not adopt open-source if there is no mitigation for this risk.

All projects seem to have open-source focus (building on OS components and providing Open-Source tools and platforms, together with enablers for devices), which seems logical due to the topics of the relevant calls in the recent years. The CSAs promote the open-source developments and architectures, nevertheless there is a segmentation of solutions resulting as each RSA seems to develop their own framework/platform as an extension of a previous one. No clear strategy is visible, how this collection, which can result in a solution that is easy to adapt for industry (certification needs, maintenance, support on long run, etc.). As to the general open source efforts, every project starts building its own community, rather than running all together under one brand/logo that is maintained longer than project lifetime. More coordinated approach would benefit the open source application.

It looks like current projects build on previous outcomes. They compose their frameworks and platforms for architectures from components from previous actions. Some longer-term initiatives drive platforms (MetaOS) which are applied by recent projects. It is unclear how experiences from project's use cases are fed back from RIAs to the platform maintaining initiatives, and if the learnings are integrated so that future versions benefit from experiences taken from earlier PoCs from other projects. Maybe dedicated feedback workshops at the end of RIAs should be organized by the CSAs to collect the learnings from the

implemented PoCs, for the further development and maintenance of the future versions of platforms and components.

The projects are organized in clusters, which themselves operate exclusively under the umbrella of the EU-CEI initiative. Of course, there is cooperations with ECLIPSE and similar Open-Source Tool initiatives or repositories (Git-Hub). Connections towards the security initiative are weak. None of the projects employs security testing approaches etc. which would be different if more parties with dedicated security background would be participating/cooperating. Same accounts for security/safety certification activities which will be required for many applications in areas like aviation, automotive, e-health, critical infrastructures etc.

The security certification schemes for components and applications are missing for proper adoption in areas with security and/or safety requirements (payment, grid, aviation, automotive, health etc.). These certification community is not moving fast, setting up certification schemes and labs requires long time and this may prevent proper adoption of the technology by the market. No activity in this direction is visible now by the projects.

Role of programming tools within the swarm cluster / reuse of tools across projects

Maybe the whole section can be deleted. Swarm intelligence poses unique challenges to traditional edge and cloud programming methods and tools due to the decentralised and self-organising nature of such systems. This report examines the programming models and tools adopted by the five projects in the swarm compute cluster funded under the HORIZON-CL4-2024-DATA-01-03 topic.

Session on this topic of Programming tools for decentralised intelligence and swarms did not go into the detail of the swarm effects. The work shop in general presented swarm computing applications, which need to be able to work unattended on the provided infrastructure. This could be a single IoT device, while changing location or duplicating in runtime when functional operations require this. For instance, more data is requested or provided to handle than a single component can manage. Example given is a swarm of drones collaborating that can be extended when needed to extend capacity or when devices or lost (physical or connected).

To fill this gap, the report briefly examines existing programming tools and models developed by the project by analysing existing public deliverables and documents made accessible to the author. This included Tardis deliverables on “First programming models and API” (D3.1) and “Integrated Development Environment “(D3.2) and some background document on the INCODE project (project proposal).

Generally, swarm applications in the context of these projects are distributed applications that must run across a heterogeneous range of computational resources that are part of an edge-cloud continuum while being able to self-adapt to changes to the underlying resource substrate. This requires some way to specify

such swarm applications programmatically and link these to underlying services offered by their frameworks.

The Tardis project builds on top of a language-independent, event-driven programming model in which a swarm application can be described as an ensemble of concurrent, distributed, and possibly heterogeneous services that interact in an event-driven fashion over networked edge and cloud resources. Tardis services can use services provided by the Tardis toolbox through well-defined APIs, significantly simplifying swarm application development. An Integrated Development Environment is provided for application developers based on the Eclipse IDE, which provides a workflow editor and access to other Tardis toolbox services through tailored plug-ins. In the later stages of the project, support for the Visual Studio Code IDE is also envisioned.

The INCODE project follows a different programming model. Here, decentralised intelligence apps are developed on top of a distributed reasoning engine and acceleration of code for efficient computation in heterogeneous hardware. The project aims to enable software development for INCODE apps via an IDE, with a focus on supporting the distributed reasoning engine and the TornadoVM plugin, a hardware acceleration support over heterogeneous resources.

Swarm project references:

<https://openswarm.eu>

<https://www.incode-project.eu>

<https://oasees-project.eu>

<https://www.project-tardis.eu>

<https://www.smart-edge.eu>

CSA project references:

<https://eucloudedgeiot.eu>

<https://discover-us.eu>

www.hipeac.net